

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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No 3

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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MUNDARIJA

Экологические и альтернативные заполнители для бетона в условиях Узбекистана.....	10
Акрамов Хуснитдин Ахрарович, Тохиров Жалолiddин Очилович, Самадов Хомид Самандарович	
Investitsion marketingni rivojlantirish asosida mintaqa investitsiya jozibadorligini oshirish	16
Ahmedov Alim Babaniyozovich	
O'zbekistonda yashil budjetlashtirish, energiya samaradorligi va issiqxona gazlari emissiyasi.....	22
Pulatov Dilshod Haqberdiyevich, Qulliyev Ulug'bek Mirzayevich, Mamanov Alisher	
Development of the Digital Economy as a Trigger of the Economic Growth of the New Uzbekistan.....	28
Luiza Sayfullovna Makhmutkhodjaeva, Umarova Shahnoza Akbarovna	
Oliy o'quv yurtlarida matematik statistikani o'qitishning xususiyatlari.....	34
Shamsiyev Damin Najmiddinovich, Aymatova Farida Xo'razovna	
Turizm tadbirkorlikning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	37
Mardonova Dilafuz Kosimovna	
Oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi ta'minoti: O'zbekistonda mayonez importini notarif tartibga solish va ichki ishlab chiqarishni rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	41
Muratova Shohista Nimatullayevna, Nomozov Azizbek Xayrulla o'g'li	
Mamlakatimizga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishda qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorining o'rni va roli	46
Akramov Azamat Ramziddinovich	
Mamlakatning iqtisodiy va ekologik rivojlanishida elektromobil sanoatini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati	53
Iminov Mahmudjon Azimjon o'g'li	
Hududiy eksport salohiyatini oshirishning marketing strategiyasi.....	60
Jiyamuratov Rustam Nuriddinovich	
Turistik kompaniyalar moliyaviy barqarorligini baholash usullarini takomillashtirish kompaniya moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlashning muhim mezonini.....	65
Jo'rayev Behzod Nuraliyevich	
Iste'molchilarni xulq-atvori modellari asosida marketing strategiyalarini shakllantirish.....	70
Kutbitdinova Moxigul Inoyatovna	
Hisob siyosati va unda biologik aktivlar hisobini yoritib berish tartibini takomillashtirish	75
Mirzayeva Nargiza Batirovna	
Mamlakat iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishda investitsiyalarning o'rni.....	80
Otajonova Charosxon Polvonquli qizi	
Innovatsion menejment va raqamli transformatsiyalarni joriy etishning metodologik asoslari.....	84
Quldoshev Asliddin Tursunovich	
Strategik boshqaruvda xususiy kapital samaradorligini baholash.....	89
Nasriyeva Zebiniso A'zam kizi, Mavlyanova Dilobar Maxkamovna	
Mintaqalarni innovatsion rivojlantirish istiqbollari tashkiliy tuzilmalarini takomillashtirishni boshqarish yo'llari	100
Xodjamuratova Gulbaxar Yuldashevna	
Meva-sabzavot eksporti barqarorligini ta'minlashning ekonometrik tahlili	105
Shamsiyeva Feruza Muratxodjayevna	
Зарубежный опыт активизации экономической активности домохозяйств.....	111
Бердиев Гайрат Ибрагимович, Маликова Севинч Телман кизи, Люсииков Артемий Александрович	
The Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Economic Growth: A Case Study of Uzbekistan.....	116
Abdulla Ibragimov, Keldiyorov Shakhriyor Ilyos O'g'li	

Mintaqada sanoat ishlab chiqarish rivojlanishining kambag'allikni qisqartirishdagi ahamiyati	121
Abdullayev Habibullo Asadulla o'g'li	
Global iqtisodiyot sharoitida islom moliyasi mezon va tartiblarini joriy etishdagi muammolar va yechimlar	125
Abduvosidova Gulandom Abdurashid qizi	
Amerika Qo'shma Shtatlari tajribasida biznes subyektlarini toifalarga ajratish amaliyotining xususiyatlari	131
Akobirova Nodira Najmiddin qizi	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida qishloq xo'jaligini innovatsion rivojlanish yo'llari.....	135
Axmedova Nafisa Amirddin qizi	
Strategic directions of integration of Uzbekistan into the international hospitality industry	140
Bekmurodova Laylo Tursunmamatovna	
Surxondaryo viloyatida parrandachilikni rivojlantirish ko'rsatkichlarini prognozlash va modellashtirish.....	144
Bobomuratov Imomqul Islamovich	
Mamlakatimizda chorvachilik mahsulotlarini yetishtirishning hozirgi holati va uning tahlili.....	149
Talipova Dilfuza Nabiyeвна	
Agrar soha korxonalarining moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimini takomillashtirish.....	154
Erkinxojiev Ismoiljon Ikromjon o'g'li	
Analysis of the Influence of Macroeconomic Indicators on State Budget Tax Revenue	158
Meyliev O. R., Gofurova K.	
Mahalliy budjet xarajatlarini hududlar ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga ta'siri.....	166
Hazratqulov Shahboz Boboqul o'g'li	
Influence of Digital Technologies on Economic Growth of the Republic of Uzbekistan.....	170
Igamberdiyeva Kunduz Ergashevna	
Transmilliy kompaniyalarning tashqi bozorlar uchun marketing strategiyalari va marketing tadqiqotlarini o'tkazish amaliyoti	174
Jo'rayeva Zilola Turobovna, Saidova Dilnozaxon Odiljon qizi	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan investitsiya loyihalarini moliyalashni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari.....	178
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna	
Korxonalarda inqirozga qarshi moliyaviy boshqaruv tizimini takomillashtirish	183
Latipova Shaxnoza Maxmudovna	
Tijorat banklari faoliyatida onlayn tizimlarining tutgan o'rni va ularning rivojlanishi.....	188
Raxmataliyev Muzaffar Eshdavatovich	
Aholi farovonligini oshirishda tadbirkorlik faoliyatining ta'sirini baholashning nazariy asoslari	194
Fayziyeva Dilsuz Bahodirovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasini "yashil" iqtisodiyotga o'tish samaradorligini oshirish.....	200
Mirzayev Bexruz Abdulla o'g'li	
Andijon viloyatida kambag'allik darajasini qisqarishiga ta'sir etuvchi ko'rsatkichlar	214
Musaeva Ziyoda Allayarovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi qishloq xo'jaligi eksportida marketing muammolari	218
Musyeva Shoirazimovna, Agzamov Avazxon Talgatovich	
Respublikamizda parranda bosh sonining hozirgi holati va uning istiqbollari.....	223
Akramova Nargiza Axrorovna	
Menejmentda ishbiarmonlik kommunikatsiyalaridan foydalanishda optimal strategiyalarini qo'llash shart-sharoitlari.....	227
Narzullayeva Gulchehra Salimovna, Shadiyeva Madina Djaloliddin qizi	
Raqamlashtirish sharoitida innovatsion faoliyatning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	231
Nazarova Latofat Toirjon qizi	
O'zbekistonda masofaviy bank xizmatlarini rivojlantirishdagi muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari.....	235
Nurmuxammedov Matlab Yunusovich	

Davlat aktivlarini samarali boshqarish hamda nazorat qilishni takomillashtirish.....	240
Mirzayev O., Nazarov G'ayrat Olim o'g'li	
Talabalarning oilali bo'lishiga ta'sir etuvchi omillarga iqtisodiy baholashda yangicha yondashuv.....	246
O. U. Shomurodov, Z. U. Uroqov, A. T. Ablahatov, A. A. Suyarov, J. S. Urazov	
Methodological Aspects for Branding in Private Schools.....	251
Odilova Sitora Sayfitdin qizi	
Совершенство процедуры оценки эффективности и результативности расходов государственного сектора.....	256
Олимов Элёр Фазлиддин угли, Искандаров Суннатилло Бахриддин угли	
Logistika xizmatlari samaradorligini oshirishda blokcheyn texnologiyalardan foydalanish	261
Rajabov Orzujon Mamasoliyevich	
Markaziy Osiyoda energetika bozorini rivojlantirishning kelgusi istiqboli va imkoniyatlari.....	267
Saidov Mash'al Samadovich, Umarova Irodaxon Nuraliyevna	
Mamlakat iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishda sug'urta bozorining innovatsion usullaridan foydalanishning konseptual asoslari	275
Narzullayeva Gulchehra Salimovna, Saidova Dilnozaxon Odiljon qizi	
Oliy ta'limda boshqaruv strategiyalari va ularni amalga oshirish mexanizmi.....	279
Saidqulova Firuza Farmonovna	
Jismoniy shaxslardan olinadigan daromadlarini soliqqa tortishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	283
Salimov Sherzod Baxtiyorovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasidagi mavjud suv resurslarining iqtisodiy holati tahlili	288
Shanazarova Gulyora Baxtiyarovna	
Tijorat banklari kredit risklarini kamaytirish yo'llari.....	294
Tulkinova Maftuna Anvarbek qizi	
The use of Intellectual Systems in the Improvement of the Educational Process Management System in Higher Educational Institutions.....	303
Umarova Dilfuza Rakhmatilla qizi	
Oliy ta'lim tizimida yangi iqtisodiy mexanizmlarni shakllantirish.....	307
Xakimov Dilshodjon Rahmonaliyevich	
Global iqtisodiy sharoitida moliyaviy hisobotlar auditida muhimlikni baholashni xalqaro stanadartlar asosida takomillashtirish.....	311
Xasanova Nasiba Tolliboy qizi	
Qurilish materiallari sanoatida innovatsion klasterlarni tashkil etish istiqbollari.....	314
Yuldasheva Kamola Miraliyevna	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida gibril bulut xizmat modelini qo'llash mexanizmini ishlab chiqish	319
Zaripov Bahodir Bobomurod o'g'li	
Роль инвестиций в системе железнодорожного транспорта в Республике Узбекистан	325
Акбарова Лайло Упашевна	
Gidrotexnik inshootlar betonlarini samaradorligini tahlil qilish va oshirish natijalari.....	330
Asqarov B. A., Karimov M. U., Xolmirzayev S.T., Obidjonov J. T.	
Maxsus iqtisodiy zonalar hududiga jalb etilgan investitsiyalar to'g'risida	334
Davlayev G'olib Ashurovich	
Yangi xizmat turi xizmatlar sohasini innovatsion boshqarishning metodologiyasi	337
Djurayeva Dilnoza Davron qizi	
Mintaqalar innovatsion salohiyatini baholashning uslubiy yondashuvlari.....	343
J. A. Ismatullayev, D. X. O'rinov	
Milliy qayta sug'urtalovchilarning xalqaro sug'urta bozoriga kirib borishi va kutilayotgan xavf-xatarlar	348
Jorabayev Jasur Abduraxmanovich	

Moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlari asosida tovarlar auditi natijalarini auditorlik hisobotida aks ettirish tartibi	354
Ibragimov M. M., Ergashev O. F.	
Turistik destinatsiyalarni tashkil etish va rivojlantirishning xorijiy tajribalari	358
Karimov Anvar Aktam o'g'li	
Jismoniy shaxslarning mol-mulk va yer soliqlarini hisoblash va undirish samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	362
Qurbonov Muxiddin Abdullayevich	
Iqtisodiy xavfsizlikning institutsional tizimini tadqiq etishga uslubiy yondashuvlar.....	367
Mamatov Axmetjon Atajanovich, Allaberganov Zakir Gayibovich	
Davlatning iqtisodiy xavfsizligini ta'minlashning nazariy jihatlarini	373
Mamatov Mamajan Axmadjonovich	
Paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlari eksport faoliyatini rivojlantirishning xorij tajribasi.....	380
Mansurov Saidxo'ja Kamalovich	
Korxonalar raqobatbardoshligini oshirish muammolari va dolzarb vazifalari	386
Musyeva Shoira Azimovna	
Устойчивый и инклюзивный рост: взаимосвязь экономического прогресса с социальным равенством и экологическим управлением	390
Нодирбек Холбаев	
Mintaqalarni investitsion jozibadorligini taraqqiyot strategiyasiga ta'sirini statistik baholash.....	396
Nuriddinov Zufar Akbarovich	
Финансирование каракулеводства: преодоление финансовых вызовов в пустынных регионах Узбекистана	402
Нуриллаев Жамолиддин Ярашевич	
O'zbekiston investitsiya muhitini yanada yaxshilash va uning jozibadorligini oshirish.....	408
Oybek Elmuratov	
Intellectual mulkning iqtisodiy mazmuni va tarixiy rivojlanish bosqichlari	411
Maxmudova Nargiza Davlyat qizi	
Implementation and use of Digital Technologies in Logistics Abstract.....	416
Kushakova Mamura, Koshakova Mukhlisa Surat qizi	
Innovatsion iqtisodiyot tushunchasining mazmun mohiyati	421
Abduqaxorov Bekzod O'tkir o'g'li	
Raqamlashtirish iqtisodiy o'sish va raqobatbardoshligini oshirish omili sifatida.....	426
Mamajonova Durdonahon Mamaruzi qizi	
O'zbekistonda tashqi savdoni notarif usullar orqali tartibga solishning mamlakat iqtisodiyotiga ta'siri.....	431
Norqobilov Akobir Iso o'g'li	
Инновационные методы переработки горных отходов для экологической устойчивости в Узбекистане	437
Аскарлов Бахтиер Аскарлович, Собирова Мукаддас Хамидуллаева	
Опыт зарубежных стран по стимулированию производства сельскохозяйственной продукции и перспективы внедрения в Узбекистан.....	442
Холиков Сулаймон Уткир угли	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda strategik boshqaruv hisobini tashkil qilishning uslubiy jihatlarini.....	447
Pardayeva Shahnoza Abdinabiyevna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik faoliyatini moliyalashtirishni statistik tahlili.....	452
Sayfullayev Siddik Nosirovich	
Sug'urta tashkilotining innovatsion risklarini baholash.....	457
Sattorov Shoxrux Maxmudjon o'g'li	

Kapital bozori rivojlanishining zamonaviy tendensiyalari	462
Turdiyeva Uzayda Omirbayevna	
Адаптивный искусственный интеллект в управлении человеческими ресурсами.....	469
Хайдарова Малика Шокирджановна	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida moliyaviy mablag'lardan samarali foydalanishga xizmat qiluvchi zamonaviy va istiqbolga mo'ljallangan huquqiy asoslarning yaratilganligi to'g'risida.....	478
Xayriddinov Shuxrat Botirovich	
Investitsiya loyihalariga ta'sir qiluvchi risklarni sifat jihatdan baholash usullarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	482
Shaislamova Nargiza Kabilovna	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan investitsion loyihalarni kreditlash tartib va ularni takomillashtirish yo'llari	491
Yunusova Ozoda Anvarjon qizi	
Hududlar iqtisodiy xavfsizligini ta'minlashda soliq salohiyatini oshirishning nazariy jihatlarini	498
E. N. Raximov	
Konsolidatsiyalashgan moliyaviy hisobot tuzishning zarurligi.....	504
Avazov Iloxom Ravshanovich	
Inson resurslarini boshqarishning innovatsion usullarini joriy etish vositalarini ishlab chiqish.....	509
Djuraeva Guzal Shavkatovna	
Agrar soha korxonalarining moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimini takomillashtirish.....	513
Erkinxojiyev Ismoiljon Ikromjon o'g'li	
Korporativ qimmatli qog'ozlar asosida korxonalarni moliyalashtirishning ilg'or xorij tajribalari.....	517
Igitov Jurabek Kuzibekovich	
The impact of corporate governance on firm performance and financial stability	524
Muhammadyor Yunusov	
Mintaqalarda kamg'allik darajasini pasaytirish va xorij tajribasidan foydalanish yo'llari.....	537
Musulmonova Shahlo Nasriddinovna	
Makroiqtisodiy barqarorlikni mustahkamlash soliq ma'muriyatchiligini samarali tashkil etish yo'llari	541
Mutalova Dilorom Maxamadjanovna, Kenjaboyeva Nigina	
Iqtisodiy savodxonlik hamda tadbirkorlik qobiliyati o'rtasidagi to'g'ri nisbatdagi bog'liqlik munosabatining fundamental asoslari.....	544
Tuxtayeva Muyassar Shovkat qizi	
Korxonalarning bankrotlik riskini baholashning xalqaro modellari.....	550
Umarova Hulkar Umidulloyevna	
O'zbekistonda korxonalar boshqaruvida kadrlar salohiyatidan foydalanish amaliyotini rivojlantirishning xorij tajribasi	555
Do'stova Aziza Qahramonovna	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida boshqaruv tizimining xususiyatlari.....	559
Iroda Majidova	
Ziyorat turizmini rivojlantirishning muhim xususiyatlari	565
Mirzayev Qulmamat Jonuzoqovich, Shukurov Tohirjon Izzatullo o'g'li	
Qandolat mahsulotlari bozorida marketing tadqiqotlarini asosiy yo'nalishlari	569
Tuychiyeva Vasila Faxriddin qizi	
“Зелёная экономика” как фактор повышения экономического роста страны.....	573
Тураева Адиба Икрамовна	
Oilada sarf-xarajatlar samarasiga erishishning muhimligi.....	580
Xasanov Rustam Rabimovich	
Aholi farovonlik darajasidagi farqlarni tartiblash yo'nalishlari.....	583
Xasanov Rustam Rabimovich, Turdiyev Zoxidjon Rustamovich	

Совершенствование оценки стоимости объектов недвижимости в Узбекистане на основе зарубежного опыта.....	588
Хомитов К. З., Халилова Л. Ш.	
Mamlakatimizda qishloq xo'jaligida kooperatsiya munosabatlarini rivojlantirishda xorij tajribalaridan foydalanishning ahamiyati.....	594
Choriyeva Nigina Kaxramonovna	
Davlat xaridlari tizimini takomillashtirish yo'llari	598
Alimbayeva Sevara Alimbayevna	
Yengil sanoatni rivojlanishida Germaniya tajribasi.....	601
F. Jumaniyazova, G'ulomov Ibroxim Rustam o'g'li	
The efficiency of usage of Islamic finance instruments in security market.....	607
Khasanov Umarbek Begmat ugli	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlari eksportini rivojlantirishda raqamli platformalardan foydalanishning xorijiy tajribalari va ulardan foydalanish yo'llari.....	613
Mamasoatov Dilshod Ravshanovich	
O'zbekistonda kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik subyektlarini tashkil qilinishining hozirgi holati va muammolari	621
Nutfulloev Tolib G'olib o'g'li	
Mehnat bozorida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish metodologiyasini takomillashtirish	627
Maxammadiyev M. M.	
Ishlab chiqarishni modernizatsiya qilish sharoitida mahsulot tannarxini optimallashtirish asoslari.....	632
Narzullayeva Gulchehra Salimovna	
Elektron pullarni rivojlantirish yo'llari	636
Rustamov Maqsud Suvonqulovich, Egamberganov Mirzabek Odilbek o'g'li	
Загрязнение окружающей среды в Узбекистане: проблемы, причины и пути решения	644
Ишонкулова Феруза Асатовна, Шукуров Тимур Умидович	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida tijorat banklarini transformatsiyalash modeli orqali takomillashtirish	649
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich, Norova Nozima Nabiyevena	
Land Tax Received From Individuals and its Share in the Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan	656
Hakimov Feruz Khurshid ugli	
O'zbekistonda "yashil" iqtisodiyot va iqlim o'zgarishi bilan bog'liq xarajatlar tahlili.....	659
Isaxonova Ruxshona Muzaffar qizi, Sharapova Mashxura Azadovna	
Qurilish xizmatlari ma'lumotlar tizimini takomillashtirish imkoniyatlari.....	665
Nurfayziyev Zayniddin Boymurodovich, Nurfayziyev Elyor Zayniddinovich	
Ipotekali kreditlashni rivojlantirishning xorijiy davlatlar tajribasi va uni O'zbekistonda tatbiq etish yo'llari	670
Turdiyev Shaxriddin Erxonovich	
Suv resurslaridan foydalanishda xorij tajribalari	675
Berdiyev Anvar Abdivaliyevich	
Auditda yetarli va mos dalillarni to'plash tartibi	681
Meliyev Isroil Ismoilovich	
"Yashil" iqtisodiyot konsepsiyasining shakllanishi va rivojlanishi.....	686
Urunbayev Saparbek Samatovich	
Uy-joy fondini boshqarish samaradorligini oshirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	692
Xolmuradov Raxmatilla Ne'matillaevich	
O'zbekiston mahsulotlarining tashqi bozordagi raqobatbardoshligi xususiyatlari va onlayn platformalar.....	699
Baymuradov Shoxrux Maxmudovich	
Factors affecting investment attractiveness in the global investment landscape.....	704
Otaboev Akhmed Makhsudbek o'g'li, Juliana Juliana, Fazliddin Nasriddinov	

Xalqaro migratsiyaning O'zbekiston mehnat bozori va inson kapitaliga ta'siri.....	709
Tilabova Kumush Farhod qizi	
Анализ и оценка естественного освещения помещений образовательных учреждений.....	714
Пирмухамедова Шахноза	
Актуальные вопросы укрепления доверия населения к банковской системы Республики Узбекистан...	719
Рузибоева Нилуфар Тулкин кизи	
Методические подходы к формированию механизмов стратегического управления развитием химической отрасли.....	725
Бибутова Шахло Саъдуллаевна	
Iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda erkin iqtisodiy zonalarini tashkil etishning afzalliklari va muammolari	730
Axmedova Dilbar Buronovna	
Natijaga yo'naltirilgan budjetlashtirishda sog'liqni saqlash muassasalarini moliyalashtirishning mohiyati.....	734
Ishmanova Diana Nurmamadovna	
Oziq-ovqat sanoatini tashkiliy-iqtisodiy jihatdan rivojlanti-rishning nazariy asoslari	737
Muxtorova Madina Azamat qizi	
Ipoteka kreditlari sohasidagi islohotlar va kelajakdagi istiqbollari	741
A'zamxo'jayeva Nihola Sulaymon qizi	
Sanoat ishlab chiqarish tizimining investitsion xususiyatlari	746
Yodgorova Xalima To'liqinovna	
Budjet ijrosini samarali ta'minlashda davlat xaridlarining ahamiyati.....	752
Sholdarov Dilshod Azimiddin o'g'li, Fayzullayeva Zilola Ravshanovna	
Aholi sog'ligi – milliy boylikning tarkibi va jamiyat taraqqiyotining muhim shartidir.....	763
Djumabayeva Shaira Xalillayevna	
Moliyaviy hisobotlarning xalqaro standartlari: hisob siyosati.....	769
Rizayev Nurbek Kodirovich, Mamatova Charos Shavkiddinovna	
Milliy iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda investitsion muhitning o'рни	778
Valiyeva Sayyora Xushbaqovna	
Davlat ishtirokidagi korxonalarda korporativ ijtimoiy mas'uliyat ("Rossiya temir yo'llari" OAJ misolida).....	784
Xidirova Marg'uba Rustamovna, Saidqulov Avazbek Botirqul o'g'li	
Raqamli transformatsiyaning O'zbekistonning investitsion jozibadorligiga ta'siri	790
Saitkamolov Muxammadxo'ja Sobirxo'ja o'g'li, Markabayeva Jansaya Aybek qizi	

THE USE OF INTELLECTUAL SYSTEMS IN THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article analyzed the theory of using intellectual systems that manage quality assurance in higher education institutions, and studied its scientific and practical results. The article covered a review of scientific theoretical views, an analysis of the literature on intelligent systems and LMS. The intellectual systems used in the higher education system of Uzbekistan were studied and analyzed. The design and implementation of the intelligent educational management system was analyzed using Fuzzy Clustering algorithm models.

Key words: Intellectual information system, quality management process, LMS, e-learning, electronic university.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalarida sifatni ta'minlashni boshqaradigan intellektual tizimlardan foydalanish nazariyasi tahlil qilingan va uning ilmiy va amaliy natijalari o'rganilgan. Maqolada ilmiy nazariy qarashlar sharhi, intellektual tizimlar va LMS bo'yicha adabiyotlar tahlili yoritilgan. O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim tizimida qo'llanilayotgan intellektual tizimlar o'rganilib, tahlil qilindi. Intellektual ta'limni boshqarish tizimini loyihalash va joriy etish Fuzzy Clustering algoritmi modellari yordamida tahlil qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: Intellektual axborot tizimi, sifatni boshqarish jarayoni, LMS, e-learning, elektron universitet.

Аннотация: В данной статье проанализирована теория использования интеллектуальных систем управления обеспечением качества в высших учебных заведениях, изучены ее научные и практические результаты. В статье представлен обзор научно-теоретических взглядов, анализ литературы по интеллектуальным системам и LMS. Были изучены и проанализированы интеллектуальные системы, используемые в системе высшего образования Узбекистана. Проектирование и реализация интеллектуальной системы управления образованием были проанализированы с использованием моделей алгоритма нечеткой кластеризации.

Ключевые слова: Интеллектуальная информационная система, процесс управления качеством, LMS, электронное обучение, электронный университет.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the higher education system is paying a lot of attention to the use of smart learning environments in the organization of teaching processes. In this regard, the issue of managing the educational process based on the introduction of information and communication technologies in our country was raised. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the National Personnel Training Program" dated August 29, 1997 and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 30, 2002 "On Further Development of Computerization and Introduction of Information and Communication Technologies" prompted the beginning of reforms in the field of education.. According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to introduce the form of distance education in higher education institutions", the fields of bachelors education and masters degree, where it is not possible to introduce the form of distance education determination of specialties by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, organization of distance education using a special platform or using existing platforms, determination of the procedure for the admission of students to distance education and the organization of the educational process, as well as distance education Issues of organization of education quality monitoring were shown.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

A.V. Ostroux's work promoting the conceptual foundations of using intelligent information systems should be highlighted. The problems of the connection of economic sectors with the educational system are described in the educational literature of our country's scientists ETMannopova, GNOKhunova, R. Alimov, BA Begalov, NM Makhmudov, Sh. Shodiyev and others.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this case, prediction of students' achievements based on Fuzzy C-means (FCM) and Collaborative Filtering (CF) was performed in FCM-CF models. The model has better predictive performance and is more suitable for predicting the exam scores of students in the higher education management system. The innovation of the intelligent learning management system is that it has two more functions in addition to the main data management function:

- predictive analytics for student performance and predicting teacher evaluations. It can support data to improve the quality of education.

To ensure that the system is practical, relevant educational standards and systems should be taken as a benchmark.

Principle of System Openness and Commonality: The design of systems should be open in order to facilitate the sharing of information and data and the operation of users across platforms.

Fig. 1: Design principles of educational management system

Principle of ease of access: Most of the educational process is relatively easy to manage, therefore, the operation of the system should provide simple and quick access to facilitate management.

The principle of easy update: The complexity and variety of information requires that the learning management system be easy to update and subsequently improve.

Principle of security and reliability: Educational process management systems should have a high level of security and stability.

The electronic requirements for the functions of the educational process management system mainly include:

Build and manage academic status database, enter and edit academic data.

Forming a general educational plan for the institute, issuing a curriculum for the institute and drawing up a curriculum for teachers and review of the curriculum by the academic administration.

Entering, querying, editing and statistics of educational materials.

Extracting curriculum information from academic activities

selection of courses by administration, survey and students, consolidation of course selection data and re-selection of courses.

Setting the place and time of the inspection, selecting and identifying the supervisor and other requests for relevant information.

Statistical analysis of students' scores by teachers, automatically by the system on the individual performance of students, and input and editing of student requests and complaints.

Conducting teacher self-evaluations, evaluations by students, colleagues, and supervisors, and statistical analysis of evaluation data.

The LMS system is used to perform the following tasks and achieve these goals:

1. Education process to manage automation and centralization.
2. Students to them access opportunity provision for educational materials placement.
3. Remote teaching technologies (DLT) standards maintain relevance.
4. Education materials again use provision, education personalization of content.
5. Education process participants between mutually cooperation opportunities to do and tools expand.

Of the educational process management system is structured as follows (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Architecture of educational process management system

Training courses and modules are created in the LMS structure. LMS's structure is one of the most important parts for managing the learning process. With the help of this structure, students and teachers will be able to perform their tasks and manage the educational process. Each course or module provides students with the opportunity to study a specific topic.

Learning materials such as video tutorials, e-books, audio files, quizzes and other supplementary materials are stored in the LMS.

Currently, there are two methods of mixed C/S and B/S model: one is called "request/change" model, and the other is called "internal/external" model (Figure 3-4). In the B/S and C/S mixed software architecture of the "request/change" model, regardless of whether users connect to the system via the Internet or LAN, if the maintenance and change of data operations if necessary, the C/S architecture is required to be used. This table lists several uses as an "Information System". "Request / change" model, which provides information search and learning for users of the system. The "internal/external" model shows internal resources (books, journals, reference books) and external resources (websites, personal blogs, social networks) for reading educational materials available in this system. If only general query and view operations are performed, B/S architecture is used.

In conclusion, it can be said that the architecture and components of HE portal integrated with educational environments should meet the functional requirements.

To date, the higher education system uses information systems created on the basis of the internal capabilities of HEI (by HEI employees) and information systems developed by other companies or created according to specific needs.

Software products developed by companies can be divided into the following according to their functional characteristics:

- complex software products;
- monolithic systems, i.e. systems where additional functions cannot be implemented;
- modular systems, that is, systems that can be connected to the existing information system as an additional module, with the possibility of adding new functions to the overall system;
- platforms for creating automated management systems;
- server components;
- special development tools;
- A separate program or module created for the purpose of automating the activities of the HEI or its department;
- test or training process

CONCLUSION

The architecture and components of the HEI portal combined with educational environments should meet the overall functional requirements.

To date, the higher education system uses information systems created on the basis of the internal capabilities of HEI (by HEI employees) and information systems developed by other companies or created according to specific needs.

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- Platforms for creating automated management systems;
- server components;
- special development tools;
- a separate program or module created for the purpose of automating the operation of the otm or its department;
- automation of the test or training process (designed to control the quality of the training process).

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